

Research

The importance of Trade, Energy efficiency and Industrial restructuring in BRICS economies

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Trade openness and Industrial restructuring are crucial for the development and growth of the economy. Industrial restructuring has been developing and growing with regards to more services rendered in different sectors. The fast pace of development has changed technology and has started a new era called the fourth industrial revolution. There has been an increase in the rendering of services, and this has become a vital aspect in the development of the service industry of energy. The Green Economy is a concept that arose after more countries moved towards the use of renewable energy. The Green economy is a new agenda that is important in the development of countries and an important factor for sustainable development of the BRICS bloc and other BLOCS. The growth of economies is the focus of the bloc and renewable energy can bring about the green economy which will develop through industrial restructuring. Energy efficiency correlates with renewable energy, as it creates a situation where more outputs are generated for less energy. This is also affected by industrial restructuring to bring upon more industries to utilize less energy and assist in the process of industrialization and economic modernization. The following study highlights the significance of BRICS countries in terms of the trade and industrial restructuring relationship and its effect on energy efficiency. It serves as evidence of the importance of the different aspects of energy on BRICS, which is also one of the notable factors to analyze and consider. Different literatures and studies are used to analyze and provide an in-depth understanding of the relationship between the three components in BRICS countries and the significance and contribution to the development of the BRICS BLOC.

Keywords: BRICS, Energy efficiency, Industrial restructuring, Trade, Imports, Exports**Introduction**

Energy efficiency has become an important aspect of the global pursuit of sustainable development. According to Rehfeldt et al. (2021), the need to make our energy systems more efficient whilst minimizing degradation due to environmental impacts and pursuing economic development, has prompted countries to reconsider their industrial and trade policies. This is particularly pronounced in BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa), where these countries are key players in the global economy and significant energy consumers. The combination of these countries accounts for over 40% of the planet's population and a considerable portion of global energy demand. Shifting to energy efficient economies is inevitable for reaching global sustainability goals, and developing countries have the potential to do so. Potential solutions have been initiated for energy efficiency improvements by industrial restructuring. Industrial restructuring is changing the setting off industries in the direction of sectors and technologies that require less

energy whilst maintaining or improving productivity. Structural changes in manufacturing have accompanied growth in high-technology and service sectors with comparatively low energy requirements, with some improvements in energy performance (Sorrell, 2009). In contrast, the paradigm of trade restructuring focuses on altering trade flows by facilitating the trade of goods and services that have a low energy footprint and importing energy saving technologies. These processes can collectively reshape the economy and reduce the carbon footprint of BRICS countries (Copeland & Taylor, 2004).

Industrial restructuring is a shift from manufacturing industries to service industries for the improvement of livelihoods, technology and increase in employment, which in turn, will be beneficial and increase the GDP of a country. According to Narayan et al. (2007), this has caused the urgency for the major economies of the world to make improvements in energy efficiency and this has resulted in research being conducted to investigate ways to minimize energy consumption to avoid the waste of energy and pollution, and contribute to the development of sustainability. To move toward an efficient global economy in terms of the usage of resources, countries need to assess and estimate the countries' potential for energy saving and reduction in emissions on the basis of the growth of the economy. This analysis can also provide useful information for decision-making processes for energy and environmental policy making, and contribute towards the sustainable development of those countries which have an effect on world economies. The use of the monetary base is used in macroeconomics which the level of energy efficiency is measured and refers to the current consumption of energy per production unit. The role of industrial restructuring is crucial in macroeconomics with its focus on service industries which generates outputs of services with minimal energy that should lead to higher quantities of goods and services supply.

In this context, the BRICS economies face specific challenges and opportunities, in which the countries that have a higher level of living standards have higher economic growth rates, larger industrial infrastructures, and many natural resource reserves (Peters, 2016). China and India are major global manufacturers and also among the world's largest greenhouse gas emitters, mainly because of their dependence on coal and other fossil fuels. Due to Brazil's abundant renewable energy resources, particularly from hydropower, its energy profile is significantly shaped, but the industrial sector still remains energy intensive (Hertel et al., 2010). Russia and South Africa are major natural resource exporters that face the dual challenge of diversification and energy efficiency. These dynamics highlight trade and industrial restructuring as sustainable development mechanisms.

Energy efficiency and BRICS Trade

Energy and trade are factors that are important in the internal affairs of the economy and the welfare and progress of the various sectors within the economy. The energy consumption phenomenon is giving away to energy efficiency to build economies that deliver better environmental and social quality for its citizens. International trade is a significant element to ensure that exports, imports and foreign direct investment are all sustainable and beneficial to the development and growth of different nations. Energy efficiency was formulated to help address issues of energy scarcity/poverty, diminished energy intensity, increased clean energy mix, increased energy access and consumption, reduced energy prices, reduced environmental footprints, and improved human welfare. Various BLOCs have discussed energy efficiency and how to protect the environment through CO₂ emission reduction, this has resulted in policies and agendas put into place to allow it to happen. The BRICS BLOC: A New Bloc of developing countries, has an agenda for the BLOC which includes energy efficiency and more industrial restructuring and trade among the countries. The original idea of the BRIC (Brazil, Russia, India, China) originated in 2001, but it wasn't until 2011 that South Africa joined the efforts of the group, creating the new signature BRICS. Most BRICS are still developing countries and follow the trends of behaviour as specified by the traditional theories that still exist. The era of globalization and international trade within the blocs brought with it a new set of theories which in most of them opposed the basic premises on which the traditional trade theorist's operated.

Energy efficiency means using energy in a more effective way to provide the same service that is conventional and uses less efficient means. Energy efficiency is the effort to lessen the energy usage and still produce the needed energy output. It is done with renewable energy sources like solar, wind and hydro and also by altering power consumption which is optimized with no loss of the outcomes which have to be forthcoming. It may be the quotient of useful outputs: vs energy inputs for a system which may be an individual energy conversion device, a building, an industrial process, a firm, a sector or an entire economy. The measure of energy efficiency in all cases will depend on what 'useful' means and what is considered as the inputs and outputs (Patterson, 1996).

The BRICS countries including Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa are significant global economic players and their energy consumption prints have high environmental consequences. There have been studies that focus on the effect of trade and industrial restructuring on energy efficiency of BRICS economies. These studies will indicate how trade and industrial restructuring can be used more positively for energy efficiency in developed countries. The BRICS' population (40%), GDP (25% nominal and US\$ 16.039 trillion), land coverage (30%), world trade (18%) and world forex (US\$ 4 trillion) make it truly important for the global economy. The BRICS as a group has engaged in sectoral collaboration across several fields, including science and technology, trade promotion and facilitation, energy, health, education, innovation, and combating transnational crime, since 2001 until the end of 2010. Now, sectoral cooperation involves over 30 subject areas. Those fields have led to particular advantages for the population of the bloc nations (Iqbal, 2021).

The BRICS meeting which took place in 2014 was held for the 11th time in Brazil it focused on the establishment of strategic and core institutions such as the New Development Bank (NDB) and the Contingent Reserve Arrangement (CRA). The institutions have far sweeping consequences and the implications for the global world at large and BRICS economies. Both the initiatives are playing a crucial role in the process of accelerating economic growth leading to socioeconomic development in the member countries of the group. Over the past five years, NDB has approved 70 infrastructure and sustainable development projects worth US\$ 25.07 billion, including loans made under the NDB Emergency Assistance Facility, across the member countries. Of these countries, 18 projects that cost US\$ 6.9 billion are from India. The 12th Summit meeting held in Russia on December 20, 2020, opened new vectors such as the world stability, common security, and modern growth. These are sine-quo-non for creating better, effective and efficient global economic order (GEO) which is the need of the hour (Iqbal, 2021)

An increase in the usage of energy consumption and the environmental effects tends to increase with economic activity, energy efficiency can provide security and other benefits like CO₂ emission reduction and import dependency reduction (Selvakkumaran & Limmeechokchai, 2013). These effects are complementary, meaning that less energy is needed per unit of economic output, increasing economic efficiency and allowing the same outputs to be produced with less energy and therefore less consumption of natural resources and less environmental impact. OECD countries are the largest consumers of energy historically. The study of Niu et al. (2011) was conducted to evaluate cause-effect relation among energy consumption, GDP growth and carbon emissions for eight countries in the Asia-Pacific over the period 1971 to 2005 found that in developing countries, carbon emissions, per capita energy consumption and the energy efficiency is significantly lower than in developed countries. The share of developed economies in the global energy consumption, however, has declined over the years. In developing countries, the relative participation showed a cumulative increase of over 100% in the last three decades.

The only growing attention among developing countries is towards the BRICS group (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa). This unprecedented political movement is a counter-diplomatic initiative aimed at bringing together the four continents through the BRICS alliance, where all members are regarded as emerging economies with tangible actions. The five nations that compose the block are generally the kind clustered together by their similarities. But separately they have distinct economic, social, political and cultural features, apart from differences in terms of histories, religions, geographies and climates. Furthermore, Leonova et al. (2007) contended that each nation has its particularities on customers, industries, growth trends, environmental governance, and resources. As a result, Armijo (2007) concluded that this region is not a homogeneous unit. There are economic features of these nations that should not be overlooked. The BRICS countries represent 20% of worldwide economy and 43% of the world population (Duarte, 2014). In fact, one of the countries with the greatest growth opportunity which is South Africa only joined the BRIC group in 2011, that's when it was changed to BRICS. In addition to its economic significance. The group will have a tremendous impact on world politics. In addition to an increase in economic development, this is due to ample land renewal and natural resources, also a great diversity and quantity of energy and experience concerning the development of technology (De Castro Camioto et al., 2016). As enumerated in the book "The Limits to Growth" by Meadows et al., (1972) there are concerns about how these countries may develop, if these countries consume at similar levels to our present economic powers which they likely will, the planet will face a catastrophic state. To mitigate carbon emissions without sacrificing economic growth, Pao & Tsai (2010) stated that BRIC countries need to expand investments in energy supply and energy efficiency, and step up conservation policies to minimize energy waste. According to World Bank data in 2010, BRICS countries energy consumption was more than the G7 countries 4213,8 * 10³ Ktoe versus 3927,5*10³ Ktoe, respectively. Hence, it is necessary to explore the nature and characteristics of this high consumption. The data envelopment analysis is used, and from the energy slacks this tool provides the total-factor energy efficiency index which is calculated for each of the BRICS countries (De Castro Camioto et al, 2016).

The stagnation of the resources dating back up to October 2023 can also precipitate economic instability and conflict, as well as underperformance. While natural resources are abundant in several countries, such as Brazil, South Africa, and India. The countries have failed to take advantage of their natural capital and have not taken advantage of their rich reserves of natural resources. This article analyzes the significance of natural resources rent and their impact on the economic development of BRICS countries over the years 1990–2020, based on such dimensions of growth as energy efficiency, financial risk, and technological innovation. It employs advanced econometric methods to estimate the parameters. The study establishes the fact that natural resources have opposite effects on the progress of the economy. The resource curse argument can thus be confirmed for the sample countries as a direct result. Moreover, technological innovation and energy efficiency improvements have both played a positive role in driving economic growth. Conversely, as economic development increases, the probability of financial loss decreases (Li et al,2023)

Thus, considering the rapid economic growth in the BRICS countries, which have been crucial to the global economy, energy use and climate governance, this study investigates the impact of energy efficiency on the environmental quality of these countries. We put the environmental quality as CO₂ emissions into our analysis, including the renewable energy in our model and estimate the association using a long-panel dataset from 29 countries for the year range 1990–2018 for estimation. The findings of our dynamic heterogeneous panel model show that energy efficiency is a significant CO₂ emission or environmental quality improvement variable in the long run and short run. In addition, we also verified the important role of renewable energy in the long run of improving environmental quality, after analyzing the negative influence of economic growth activities (Ahmed Mohamed Dahir & Masnun Mahi,2021)

There are two strands of research on international trade, and energy efficiency. The first strand is a detailed analysis. Energy is complementary to raw materials and capital, and labor as a substitute for further dependence to stimulate efficiency in the energy industry. Energy efficiency improvement and the consumption of electricity in China is due to technological changes and high energy prices, it can be argued that efficiency contributes to lower energy consumption as well (Welsch and Ochsens, 2005; Ahmed et al., 2021b; Dagar et al., 2021) From the viewpoint of endogenous technical change and international technology spill-overs, international trade also provides ways for developing countries to reach advanced technologies and machines from developed nations to mitigate the intensity of energy consumption. In terms of rapid market-oriented reform and openness, trade openness proves to be a key driver for the enhanced potential of energy efficiency in China (Elavarasan et al., 2021a; Elavarasan et al., 2021b; Gerlagh and Kuik 2014; Iqbal et al., 2021; Mani et al., 2021;Razzaq et al., 2021).

In terms of trade type, researchers continued the analysis and examined the aggregate recovery of local energy efficiency and spill-over effects released from oil imports. Other studies suggested that energy consumption increases and carbon emission rises with trade liberalization. Developing countries will also face the danger of a decline in energy efficiency in the process of free trade (Lee and Zhang 2009). The second dimension is the comparative analysis of imports and exports. From the perspective of trade products, through the analysis of input–output tables, some researchers found that the import of some energy-intensive products is one reason for the decrease of energy consumption intensity in China in 1978–1995 (Garbaccio et al., 1999). Kahrl and Roland-Holst(2008) have elaborated on this fluctuation in China's energy efficiency being mainly attributed to an increase in HS number 27 and 28 goods exports . Based on the input–output analysis, other researchers examined the embodied CO₂ emissions of China's import and export products and proposed that China should enhance its energy efficiency through electricity pricing reform and take on more renewable energy (Lin and Sun 2010).

The import and export trade scale from the perspective of the trade scale is an important determinant of industrial structure optimization, and the latter can improve energy efficiency (Chang and Hu 2010). Moreover, based on the establishment of an environmental efficiency index of 111 countries, researchers empirically verified that international trade through the increased exports and increased imports both have a relatively strong impact of environmental efficiency including energy efficiency (Doganay et al., 2014). It can be concluded that in terms of trade policy, the oil-importing countries are made increasingly vulnerable to future oil price shocks by the disappearance of their oil-import tariffs and a continuous rise in oil imports that causes deterioration of their energy efficiency (Suranovic, 1994). Due to the specific structure of China, import and export trade low–middle technology products and raw material in export trade, and middle–high technology products in import trade. Import trade is more relevant to imitation innovation in comparison to export trade (Xiaoli Hao, Xinhui Wang and Yan Xue, 2022).

Energy efficiency and Industrial Restructuring

Energy efficiency and industrial restructuring are important factors that are used in the development of BRICS economies. The relationship between the two components has been explained in some studies. According to Mingyuan and Weixuan (2016) The influence of industrial structural upgrading on energy efficiency is studied from the structural evolution direction as different directions have different influences on enterprise energy efficiency. There was a decomposition of the structural evolution direction into two dimensions of industrial structure rationalization and industrial structure optimization and evaluation of the upgrading of industrial structure, which is built based on factor productivity of labor and capital, that will analyze the influencing effect of industrial structural upgrading on energy efficiency and its growth rate using conventional, growth and elastic models. It was discovered that the impact of industrial structure evolution and direction on energy utilization efficiency and its increasing speed is prominent. Hence, the enhancement in energy efficiency is predominantly credited to the optimization of industrial structure, whereas the decline in rationalization level inhibits the growth in energy efficiency and its speed of growth.

This expansion of the gap between industrial structural rationalization and industrial structural optimization in both directions is likely to result in further adverse effects on energy efficiency and its growth rate. The increase of the proportion of clean energy in energy consumption structure is beneficial to the improvement of energy efficiency and growth rate. Hence, the future industrial policy trend should change the status of irrational industrial structure, reduce its inhibition on energy efficiency and narrow the gap of rationalization and optimization of industrial structure. Future energy demand should be reflected in the percentage of clean energy consumption, substitute energy inputs from natural and other clean energy sources and the rate of energy efficiency and its growth.

According to Yubinbin (2017) There will be increasingly serious constraints for some countries economic development such as China's economic development under the new normal on energy and the environment. While by virtue of further optimization of energy structure, there is limited space to save energy or reduce emissions, the promotion of the strategic adjustment of industrial structure is more important and realistic to improve energy efficiency. This has been empirically investigated in the adjustment to industrial structure with the two above-proposed perspectives of adjustment width and adjustment quality, that analyses the evolution characteristics of the adjustment to industrial structure and changes in energy efficiency and their correlation that tests the spatial spill-over effect that the adjustment to industrial structure has on energy efficiency.

The urban energy efficiency level of Chinese cities presents the M-type trend, and there is a significant spatial spill-over effect and interactive coupling relationship between industrial restructuring and energy efficiency; secondly, the improvement of the quality of the restructuring presents significant promotion and spatial spillover effect on energy efficiency, but the expansion of the magnitude of the restructuring has a significant inhibition effect on energy efficiency; thirdly, all places should firstly attach importance to the improvement of the quality of the adjustment to industrial structure. The energy efficiency improvement of the eastern and western regions can not only depend on the adjustment of the long-term structure and blindly restrain the second industry and develop the third industry or simply transfer industry and labor. The central region can use the spill-over effect of the quality adjustment to industrial structure to complement energy efficiency of surrounding areas and expansion to the adjustment of the industrial structure.

Wei et al (2016) focused on the factor decomposition carbon emission in industrial systems through the Kaya identity and constructed a new production function for modeling upgrade of industrial structure which influences the production factor upgrading such as production technology, capital, and labor on the low-carbon development of the industrial system. The research discovered energy structure changes, drove the low-carbon development of China's industrial system. Large numbers of high-carbon coal utilization increased the carbon emission density of the industrial system. Industrial restructuring and energy efficiency correlate with each other. This is seen in the effect that industrial restructuring has on different industries in the economy and how the expansion of the industries is impacted to increase the growth of economies. Energy efficiency is affected by industrial restructuring, through the role it plays in the green economy and its effect on economic factors.

How Trade and Industrial Restructuring Can Improve Energy Efficiency: Case Study of BRICS Countries

Business and industrial reform are vital pathways towards energy efficiency for developing countries. This analysis evaluates the influence of these processes on energy efficiency improvements in BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, and China, and South Africa), referring to papers published since 2000.

Brazil

To examine how industrial organization relates to energy efficiency in Brazil, the evidence is seen in the improvement of the interrelationship of trade liberalization and energy efficiency. According to various research, Brazil's energy conservation took place in the country's export-led agricultural and manufacturing sectors, which were adopting energy-efficient measures to meet international standards. The sugarcane ethanol industry has achieved a gain in efficiency through the co-generation of energy from bagasse. Plus, the nation's industrial reforms have lowered energy intensity in the steel and aluminum sectors, aided by trade partnerships around cleaner technologies. Brazil faces challenges of potential trade-offs between industrial development and environmental impact. Modernized energy infrastructure requires investments to enable the implementation of measures that lead to improvements in energy efficiency (Ribeiro & Schaeffer, 2008).

Russian Federation

Apart from energy-intensive sectors, Russia's industrial restructuring efforts have also been guided by its large endowments of energy resources and the need to modernize them. Trade pacts with the European Union have incentivized the adoption of energy-efficiency technologies in industries like metallurgy and petrochemicals. The reforms made after the year 2000, aimed at reducing energy losses in transmission lines, has caused the improvement of overall efficiency. Russia's reliance on fossil resources and limited variety of exports/dimensions of trade partners has raised concerns. The progressive combination of digital and renewable energy solutions within industrial operations is a prerequisite for enhancing energy efficiency (Liu & Lu, 2018).

India

India has enhanced energy efficiency with reforms in industrial policy and trade integration. The National Mission on Enhanced Energy Efficiency (NMEEE) and some energy efficiency initiatives, such as the Perform, Achieve, and Trade (PAT) plan, encourage enterprises to adopt practices with greater energy efficiency. The enhancement of energy optimization in manufacturing industries textiles, cement, and chemicals, for instance have been made possible through the importation of sophisticated machinery, utility of gas, which has also been enabled through trade liberalization. However structural hurdles such as reliance on coal-driven energy and aging infrastructure hamper progress. Sustainable efficiency improvements require enhancing public private collaborations and improving accessibility of renewable energy technology (Mukherjee et al., 2017).

China

China notably stands apart from other BRICS states because of the considerable increase in energy efficiency, it achieved through the combination of forced industrial restructuring and pragmatic trade policies. Export-centered firms have adopted the latest in production technology to meet stringent international energy requirements. As part of the 11th and the 12th Five-Year Plans, mandatory energy efficiency targets were also set with a focus on energy-intensive sectors including cement, steel and manufacturing. China's Belt and Road Initiative allowed for technology transfer, which ultimately improves energy efficiency in domestic and partner nations as well. However, regional discrepancies in energy efficiency and environmental impacts from rapid industrialization are still challenges for the country (Zhou et al., 2019).

South Africa

South Africa's transition strides toward industrial and trade restructuring have focused on reducing energy intensity in the mining and manufacturing sectors. The adoption of energy-efficient technologies has thus been driven by trade agreements and foreign funding. The Industrial Energy Efficiency Project (IEE) has substantially reduced energy consumption in key industries. Yet South Africa's reliance on coal and its outdated infrastructure limit its ability to improve energy efficiency. These challenges can be alleviated through policy reforms aimed at diversifying the energy

mix and stimulating innovative technologies to widen energy efficiency (Kohler, 2020).

The above case studies show multiple ways that reflect how trade and industrial restructuring are key for BRICS energy efficiency. The countries use different technologies, resources and policies for using the method that can optimize trade and energy efficiency for the growth and improvement of the economies.

Conclusion

Trade and industrial restructuring have a profound impact on economies, especially as they navigate periods of transition and rapid growth. The ability of nations to outpace economic downturns and inefficiencies in a short span of time is closely linked to how effectively they implement structural reforms and optimize their industries. Among the key factors influencing this process, energy efficiency emerges as a critical element, shaping not only the sustainability of industries but also their long-term competitiveness in the global market.

The evolution of economic development and the strategic utilization of industrial structures have occurred gradually, influenced by technological advancements, policy shifts, and global market trends. This transformation has been particularly evident within the BRICS bloc—comprising Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—where industrial and trade policies have played a central role in shaping economic trajectories. These nations have experienced significant shifts in production processes, infrastructure development, and resource management, all of which contribute to their ability to optimize energy use while sustaining economic growth.

With the implementation of new policies, regulations, and efficiency-driven initiatives, BRICS nations have recognized the need to balance industrial expansion with sustainable energy consumption. Factors such as imports, exports, foreign direct investment, and technology transfer have become instrumental in driving energy efficiency improvements. The adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques, renewable energy integration, and smart infrastructure solutions has further enhanced the ability of these economies to reduce waste and increase productivity.

Moreover, the interconnected nature of global trade has accelerated knowledge exchange and cross-border collaboration, allowing emerging economies to adopt best practices from leading industrialized nations. By leveraging technological innovations and modernizing industrial frameworks, countries can create a more energy-efficient and resilient economic environment. These strategic advancements not only promote sustainable development but also strengthen global competitiveness, enabling economies to achieve long-term prosperity.

Ultimately, the extent to which nations embrace trade and industrial restructuring as tools for energy efficiency will determine their ability to foster sustained economic expansion. As economies continue to evolve, integrating energy-conscious policies and technological innovations will be crucial in ensuring both industrial growth and environmental sustainability. By prioritizing energy efficiency within trade and industry, economies can achieve a more balanced and forward-looking approach to development, positioning themselves for a more competitive and sustainable future.

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References

- [1] Armijo, L. E. (2007). The BRICS countries (Brazil, China, Russia and China) as analytical category: mirage or insight? *Asian Perspective*, 31(4), 7-42.
- [2] Chang, T.-P., & Hu, J.-L. (2010). Total-factor energy productivity growth, technical progress, and efficiency change: An empirical study of China. *Applied Energy*, 87(10), 3262–3270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.04.026>
- [3] Copeland, B. R., & Taylor, M. S. (2004). Trade, growth, and the environment. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 42(1), 7–71. <https://doi.org/10.1257/002205104773558047>
- [4] Dagar, V., Khan, M. K., Alvarado, R., Rehman, A., Irfan, M., Adekoya, O. B., et al. (2021). Impact of Renewable Energy Consumption, Financial Development and Natural Resources on Environmental Degradation in OECD Countries with Dynamic Panel Data. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*, 1–11. doi:10.1007/s11356-021-16861-4
- [5] Dahir, A. M., & Mahi, M. (2021). Does energy efficiency improve environmental quality in BRICS countries? Empirical evidence using dynamic panels with heterogeneous slopes. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(8), 12027-12042. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-16410-z>. Epub 2021 Sep 24.
- [6] De Castro Camioto F, Moralles HF, Mariano EB, do Nascimento Rebelatto DA (2016) Energy efficiency analysis of G7 and BRICS considering total-factor structure. *J Clean Prod* 122:67–77
- [7] Doganay, S. M., Sayek, S., & Taskin, F. (2014). Is environmental efficiency trade inducing or trade hindering? *Energy Economics*, 44, 340–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2014.04.004>
- [8] Elavarasan, R. M., Pugazhendhi, R., Shafiullah, G. M., Irfan, M., & Anvari-Moghaddam, A. (2021). A hover view over effectual approaches on pandemic management for sustainable cities - the endowment of prospective technologies with revitalization strategies. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 68, 102789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.102789>
- [9] Garbaccio, R. F., Ho, M. S., & Jorgenson, D. W. (1999). Why has the energy-output ratio fallen in China? *The Energy Journal*, 20(3), 3. <https://doi.org/10.5547/ISSN0195-6574-EJ-Vol20-No3-3>
- [10] Hao, X., Wang, X., & Xue, Y. (2022). International spillover effect of import trade on energy efficiency in the post-COVID-19 era: Evidence from China. *Frontiers in Energy Research*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358191595_The_International_Spillover_Effect_of_Import_Trade_on_Energy_Efficiency_in_the_Post-COVID-19_Era_Evidence_From_China
- [11] Hertel, T. W., Tyner, W. E., & Birur, D. K. (2010). Global impacts of biofuel mandates. *Energy Journal*, 31(1), 75–100. <https://doi.org/10.5547/ISSN0195-6574-EJ-Vol31-No1-4>
- [12] Hsiao-Tien Pao, Chung-Ming Tsai. CO2 emissions, energy consumption and economic growth in BRIC countries. Volume 38, Issue 12, December 2010, Pages 7850-7860
- [13] Iqbal, N., Abbasi, K. R., Shinwari, R., Guangcai, W., Ahmad, M., & Tang, K. (2021). Does exports diversification and environmental innovation achieve carbon neutrality target of OECD economies? *Journal of Environmental Management*, 291, 112648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112648>
- [14] Iqbal, B. A. (2021). BRICS as a Driver of Global Economic Growth and Development. [Volume 14, Issue 1](https://doi.org/10.1177/09749101211067096) <https://doi.org/10.1177/09749101211067096>
- [15] Kahrl, F., & Roland-Holst, D. (2008). Energy and exports in China. *China Economic Review*, 19(4), 649–658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chieco.2008.05.004>
- [16] Kohler, M. (2020). The political economy of energy efficiency in South Africa. *Energy Policy*, 136, 111063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.111063>
- [17] Lee, D. J., & Zhang, J. (2009). Efficiency, equity, and environmental implications of trade liberalization: A computable general equilibrium analysis. *Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 18(3), 347–371. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638190902986504>
- [18] Li, T., Yue, X.-G., Waheed, H., & Yıldırım, B. (2023). Can energy efficiency and natural resources foster economic growth? Evidence from BRICS countries. *Resources Policy*, 83, 103643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2023.103643>
- [19] Lin, B., & Sun, C. (2010). Evaluating carbon dioxide emissions in international trade of China. *Energy Policy*, 38(1),

613–621. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.10.014>

[20] Liu, X., & Lu, Y. (2018). Energy efficiency of BRICS countries: Evidence from the multi-sectoral perspective. *Energy Policy*, 122, 599-609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.07.027>

[21] Meadows, D. H., et al. (1972). *The limits to growth*. New York: Universe Books.

[22] Mukherjee, S., Chakraborty, D., & Banerjee, S. (2017). Trade liberalization and energy efficiency in India: A sectoral analysis. *Energy Economics*, 66, 106-118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2017.06.012>

[23] Narayan., P.K, Smyth., R., &Prasad., A. (2007). Electricity consumption in G7 countries: A panel cointegration analysis of residential demand elasticities. *Energy Policy* Volume 35, Issue 9, September 2007, Pages 4485-4494

[24] Niu, S., Ding, Y., Niu, Y., Li, Y., & Luo, G. (2011). Economic growth, energy conservation and emissions reduction: A comparative analysis based on panel data for 8 Asian- Pacific countries. *Energy Policy*, 39(4), 2121-2131. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.02.003>.

[25] Patterson, M. G. (1996), 'What is energy efficiency? concepts, indicators and methodological issues', *Energy Policy*, Vol. 24, pp.377-390.

[26] Peters, G. P. (2016). The "Carbon Footprint" of global trade. *Nature Climate Change*, 6(8), 728–731. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3025>

[27] Rehfeldt, M., et al. (2021). Energy efficiency as a socio-economic challenge. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 71, 101-112.

[28] Ribeiro, S. K., & Schaeffer, R. (2008). Energy efficiency in Brazil: Lessons learned and prospects for improvement. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 12(2), 14-25. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0973-0826\(08\)60423-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0973-0826(08)60423-6)

[29] S. Selvakkumaran, B. Limmeechokchai (2013) Energy security and co-benefits of energy efficiency improvement in three Asian countries. *Environmental Science, Economics, Engineering Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews* <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Energy-security-and-co-benefits-of-energy-in-three-Selvakkumaran-Limmeechokchai/639cb37f32989a33f6849bc8ce0b3de261958561>

[30] Sorrell, S. (2009). The rebound effect: An assessment of its implications for energy policy. *Energy Policy*, 37(4), 1456–1469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.12.013>

[31] Suranovic, S. M. (1994). Import policy effects on the optimal oil price. *The Energy Journal*, 15(3), 123-144. <https://doi.org/10.5547/ISSN0195-6574-EJ-Vol15-No3-8>

[32] Welsch, H., and Ochs, C. (2005). The Determinants of Aggregate Energy Use in West Germany: Factor Substitution, Technological Change, and Trade. *Energ.Econ.* 27 (1), 93–111. doi: 10.1016/j.eneco.2004.11.004

[33] Xiaoli Hao, Xinhui Wang and Yan Xue. (2022) International Spillover Effect of Import Trade on Energy Efficiency in the Post-COVID-19 Era: Evidence from China. *Frontiers in Energy Research*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358191595_The_International_Spillover_Effect_of_Import_Trade_on_Energy_Efficiency_in_the_Post-COVID-19_Era_Evidence_From_China (Accessed 14 February 2025)

[34] Yu Binbin (2017) How Does Industrial Restructuring Improve Regional Energy Efficiency? An Empirical Study Based on Two Dimensions of Magnitude and Quality[J]. *Journal of Finance and Economics*, 2017, 43(1): 86-97.

[35] Zhang Wei , Zhu Qigui, and Gao Hui (2016) Upgrading of Industrial Structure Optimizing of Energy Structure, and Low Carbon Development of Industrial System) (a: Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics. b: Shanghai Jiao tong University; c: Chengdu University of Technology) JEL Classification: Q29, Q49

[36] Zhou, N., Levine, M., & Price, L. (2019). Overview of current energy efficiency policies in China. *Energy Policy*, 38(11), 6439-6452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.06.001>

